

Impacts of industrialization and infrastructure developments on the flora, fauna and ecosystems of the Sundarbans and surrounding areas

Abdullah Harun Chowdhury^{1*}

¹Environmental Science Discipline, Khulna University, Khulna-9208, Bangladesh. E-mail: aharunc_ku@yahoo.com; aharunc@ku.ac.bd

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Abstract

The impacts of rapid industrialization in the periphery of the Sundarbans on the flora and fauna (tiger, deer, crocodile, dolphin, fishes, etc.) and ecosystem of the Sundarbans, surrounding areas and on the other components like river banks erosion, livelihoods of the people, etc. of the Sundarbans and surroundings areas were studied to develop a guideline for future conservation and restoration. The study area is 20 km inside and outside (Periphery) of the Sundarbans under Mongla and Rampal *upazilas* of Bagerhat district, Bangladesh. Fortnight sampling was carried out and air, water, soil and biological samples were studied in the field and laboratory. The recorded data indicate that the present condition of Sundarbans and its surrounding area has reflected a sign of threatened environment. The Sundarbans has lost both floral and faunal diversity by the years. Tigers are disappeared, fishes lost their habitat, trees are affected with unknown diseases, other faunal diversity are also disappeared, erosion is concentrated along the Pashur River, people are being helpless and migrated their occupation. The industries have also brought the curse for natural environment of this area by discharging waste, gases, hot water recklessly into river and surrounding water bodies. As a result the world largest mangrove forest- Sundarbans may can lose its recognition as world heritage site.

Keywords: *Impacts, Industrialization, Flora-fauna, Ecosystems, Sundarbans*

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1. Introduction

The Sundarbans is a fragile ecosystem and the largest single tract mangrove forest in the world that has been declared Ramsar Site and Natural World Heritage, which is situated in the South-West area (21R 312-22R 382N and 89R 002-89R 552 E) of Bangladesh. It is intersected by a network of tidal canals, creeks and rivers. It is covered an area of 6,000 km² of which 3,956 km² mangrove forest lands and more than 1,800 km² water bodies (Hussain and Acharya, 1994; and IUCN, 2001). This tidal forest is very rich with natural resources, especially floral and faunal diversity like 66 species of plants, more than 200 fish species, 42 mammals, 234 birds, 51 reptiles, 8 amphibians, a lot of invertebrates, etc. (Chowdhury, 2003). More than 500 thousand peoples are directly and indirectly dependent on the Sundarbans for their livelihoods as well as socioeconomic

* Corresponding author: Abdullah Harun Chowdhury, Environmental Science Discipline, Khulna University, Khulna-9208, Bangladesh. E-mail: aharunc_ku@yahoo.com; aharunc@ku.ac.bd

purposes. Around 200 thousand people go to the Sundarbans regularly to collect the resources for their livelihoods; less than 200 thousand collect the resources seasonally and around 100 thousand people are doing business of the collected resources and they never go to the Sundarbans directly for resources extraction. Roughly 22% people's livelihoods are involved with the collection of wood resources; 5% are involved with the non-timber forest product; 69% are involved with the aquatic resources and 4% are involved with other purposes. 38% wood resource related people spend 71-75% income for their food; 33% NTFP related people spend 76-80% income for food and 50% aquatic resource related people spend 61-65% income for food which indicate that the most of the Sundarbans dependent are poor (Uddin *et al.*, 2013). 84-89% the Sundarbans dependent spend 5% income for their health; 40-68% spend 5-10% for repairing and construction of houses, and 55- 75% spend 5-7% for different social purposes like sons/daughters marriages, attending relatives marriages, religious functions, others festivals, etc. So it is clear that the Sundarbans is the prime source of livelihoods for a good number of people (Chowdhury, 2003 and 2012; and Uddin *et al.*, 2013). The findings of the different studies (Alongi, 2002; Biswas *et al.*, 2007; CEGIS, 2013; and Chowdhury, 2003, 2009, 2011, 2012 and 2017; Chowdhury and Akber, 2015; FAO, 2007; Giri *et al.* 2007; Hossain, 2014; Hussain and Acharya, 1994; IUCN, 2001; Jahan *et al.*, 2000; Mannan, 2010; Mannan *et al.*, 2012; Rahman *et al.*, 2014; Rahman *et al.*, 2013; and Sarkar, 2012) indicate that the floral and faunal composition of the Sundarbans are being changed due to some environmental threats like macro and micro climatic changes, increasing of salinity in soil and water, natural calamity, land erosion, siltation of the river beds, decreasing of the fresh water flows from the upstream, oil spills, industrialization, etc. The number of population of some high saline tolerant plants like, *Ceriops decandra*, *Excoecaria agallocha*, etc. are increasing in the low saline areas due to increasing of salinity day by day. On the other hand the number of population of low saline tolerant plants likes *Heritiera fomes*, *Xylocarpus granatum*, etc. are decreasing. Similarly populations of some faunal diversity are being decreased (Mannan, 2010; and Mannan *et al.*, 2012).

In last few years, different types of industries like coal based power plant; cement, and LPG gas factories and large infrastructures like silo are being established within 10 to 15 km periphery of the Sundarbans. According to the opinion of the local people, rapid industrialization is being happened in the Mongla and Rampal *upazilas*, which are within 10 to 15 km periphery of the Sundarbans since the inception and construction of coal based power plants in Rampal *upazila*. The raw materials and other products of those industries are being transported by different types of ships, cargoes and navigational vessels in and around the Sundarbans through the Pashur river and its connected rivers. Activities like loading-unloading, noisy ambience, lighting, speedy movements, discharging of burn and ballast water from those vessels and industries may have some direct and indirect impacts on the habit, habitat, food chain, diversity, population, etc. of the flora and fauna and ecosystems of the Sundarbans and the surroundings areas. Many workers did the research on the different issues (environmental impacts, flora and fauna, water and soil quality, food chain, oil spills, salinity intrusion, etc.) on the Sundarbans and surrounding areas. But no such quantitative data are available on the impact on the Sundarbans and surrounding areas fauna (tiger, deer, crocodile, dolphin, fishes, etc.), flora, river banks erosion, livelihoods of the people, etc. due to rapid industrialization and infrastructure developments in the periphery (within 10 to 15 km distance from the Sundarbans) of the Sundarbans.

Under these circumstances, it has become imperative to institute an investigation on the impacts on the Sundarbans and surrounding areas fauna (tiger, deer, crocodile, dolphin, fishes, etc.), flora, river banks erosion, livelihoods of the people, etc. due to rapid industrialization and infrastructure developments in the periphery of the Sundarbans for future conservation of the Sundarbans and surrounding areas ecosystems; especially the tiger and other fauna and their habitats.

2. Materials and methods

The study area is 20 km inside and outside (Periphery) of the Sundarbans (Karomjal area) under Mongla and Rampal *upazilas* of Bagerhat district, Bangladesh. The research was done in 10 permanent stations of each study area (Rampal, Mongla and the Sundarbans). Research was also done in 3 different locations of nonindustrial areas of the Sundarbans - Gharilal (22° 11' 54.80'' N 89° 20' 04.52'' E), Jorshing (22° 14' 38.97'' N 89° 21' 34.70'' E) and Kalagachia (22° 12' 22.78'' N 89° 14' 37.58'' E) of the western part of Sundarbans. Fortnight sampling was carried out from July 2015 to June 2020 and air, water, soil and biological samples were studied in the field and laboratory. Secondary data were collected from published documents and different government offices. All data were analyzed and potential environmental impacts were identified and calculated by using standard tools and methodologies (Hoshmand, 1998).

The samples of the rivers and the Sundarbans were collected by using a country boat. Water samples were collected from 10-25 cm depth by using a scale (Trivedy, 1993) for physico-chemical analysis. Physico-chemical parameters were measured *in situ* and *ex situ* conditions by following Welch (1948), APHA (1989), Mishra *et al.* (1992) and Gautam (1990). Air Pollution was measured by using High volume sampler (Envirotech APM-415). Noise pollution was measured using Sound Level Meter (Lutorn, SL-4010). Shovels and large ladders were used for collecting the soil samples according to Trivedy (1993). Soil quality were determined in the laboratory by following Jackson (1973) and Page *et al.* (1982). Planktons and benthos were studied by following Welch (1948), Transeau (1951), Edmondson (1966), Tonapi (1980), APHA (1989) and SWAMP (1007). The populations of aquatic and terrestrial plants in field were measured by following quadrat method (Ambasht, 1974). Standard observations and monitoring methods (Jayaraman *et al.*, 1998) (Foot/Pug marks per quadrat area/ a standard area curve) were followed for different faunal study. Latitude and longitude were measured by using a hand GPS meter (model GARMIN GPSMAP® 78s). Statistical analysis among the different parameters were done by following Hoshmand (1998). The investigation tools also were site observations and spot analyses; Key Informants Interview (KII); Focus Group Discussions (FGD) with community people of that area.

Impact assessment (IA): Most of the development projects produce impacts on or changes in the state of natural environment. Of which some are positive and some are negative. Similarly, some positive and negative impacts were identified in this study by following the DOE (1997) guidelines for industries, ADB (2003) environmental assessment guidelines and FPCO (1992) guidelines. These issues and impacts were evaluated in terms of distribution, quantity, quality, seasonality, ecological and socioeconomic importance. The sources of information for the scoping process were: (1) Field visits and environmental survey; (2) Collected data from different sources, departments, institutes, *upazilas*, Ups, etc. (3) Meeting with chairmen, members, local people, govt. officials, teachers, social workers, different stakeholders, etc.

Impact assessment matrix: The impact assessment matrix was done in consultation with multi-disciplinary team members. When an impact could not be quantified, qualitative judgment was used based on professional experience. The scoring were done within a 21-point score scale ranging from -1 to -10 for negative impacts and +1 to +10 for positive impacts while "0" was used for no impact (neutral impact) (Pastakia and Jensen, 1998).

Showing sampling stations-industrial sites (red star) and nonindustrial sites (yellow star)

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Physico-chemical condition of water and soil

Physico-chemical and biological conditions of water of the study areas (Rampal, Mongla and the Sundarbans mangrove forest) have been presented in Table 1 and physico-chemical conditions of the soil have been presented in Table 2.

Parameter	Unit	Present Study				Previous Study (Before 2010)			
		Mean	SD	Min	Max	Mean	SD	Min	Max
Air temperature	°C	28.2	1.9	20.7	35.3	27.9	1.6	20.3	34.5
Water temperature	°C	28.4	1.5	21.2	34.6	26.5	0.9	20.6	29.1
Transparency	cm	11	1.5	08	16	25	4	23	32
Total suspended solid	mg/l	491	137	257	678	9.5	1.8	8.9	15.8
pH		7.7	0.8	7.4	8.4	8.1	0.4	7.8	8.8
Dissolved oxygen	mg/l	5.6	0.3	3.8	6.9	6.4	0.6	4.9	7.2
Total dissolved solid	g/l	19	1.5	13.7	24	12.5	1.6	10.8	15.2
Salinity	ppt	12.9	3.7	12.1	22.6	12.2	1.5	11.6	17.5
Total hardness	mg/l	1662	143	1583	2029	952	37	815	1028
Biological oxygen demand (BOD ₅)	mg/l	3.9	0.7	2.8	5.5	2.1	0.5	1.6	2.8
Chemical oxygen demand	mg/l	365	29	281	584	133	28	75	192
Carbon dioxide (CO ₂ alk.)	mg/l	21	8	17	35	-	-	-	-
Carbonate (CO ₃ alk.)	mg/l	-	-	-	-	32	7	26	43
Bicarbonate (HCO ₃ ⁻)	mg/l	142	22	112	165	123	18	97	132
Nitrate as nitrogen (NO ₃ -N)	mg/l	3.72	0.56	2.89	4.33	2.26	0.43	2.07	3.11
Inorganic phosphate (PO ₃)	mg/l	1.90	0.07	1.76	2.03	1.72	0.07	1.53	1.84
Silicate	mg/l	5.63	0.54	4.87	6.95	5.73	0.68	4.94	6.77
Calcium	mg/l	774	66	725	880	576	49	481	690
Magnesium	mg/l	494	57	479	597	317	34	235	448
Productivity	mg/l	2.1	0.3	1.6	3.0	7.9	0.7	7.1	11.4
Oil content	mg/l	45	7	29	68	8.1	0.5	4.2	10.8
Phytoplankton (Abundance)	units/l	153	35	137	199	369	58	275	462
Phytoplankton (No. of Species)	no./l	21	6	14	30	38	5	29	51
Zooplankton (Abundance)	units/l	69	8	63	85	92	13	80	126
Zooplankton (No. of Species)	no./l	16	3	12	20	25	4	22	29
Benthos (Abundance)	no./kg	19	4	15	24	37	6	30	48
Benthos (No. of species)	no./kg	14	5	10	20	26	4	23	32

Note: - = Not detected.

Parameter	Unit	Present Study				Previous Study (Before 2010)			
		Mean	SD	Min	Max	Mean	SD	Min	Max
pH		7.6	0.2	7.5	7.9	8.2	0.2	7.9	8.5
Salinity	ppt	13.4	0.8	12.5	14.3	12.1	0.3	11.4	13.9
Total Nitrogen	%	0.26	0.019	0.20	0.28	0.16	0.005	0.12	0.19
Phosphorus	$\mu\text{g/g}$ soil	171	42	95	268	21	1.8	14	25
Sulfur	$\mu\text{g/g}$ soil	114	11	93	129	72	5	61	98
Calcium	meq/100g soil	14.3	1.2	13.4	15.5	15.8	0.4	14.6	16.5
Magnesium	meq/100g soil	10.1	0.3	9.7	10.8	11.6	1.5	10.7	12.9
Potassium	meq/100g soil	1.55	0.11	1.36	1.71	1.64	0.38	1.49	2.02
Oil content	mg/kg of 2 inch surface soil	10.7	0.9	7.5	15.6	4.8	0.4	3.4	7.6

The recorded data indicate that, high total suspended solids (491 ± 137 mg/l), total hardness value (1662 ± 143 mg/l) and content of oil (45 ± 7 mg/l) along with higher chemical oxygen demand (COD) value (365 ± 29 mg/l) were present during the period of study in the Pashur rivers and its connected canals (in and around the Sundarbans) which are being contaminated continuously by the different effluents of the different industries. On the other hand, low transparency (11 ± 1.5 cm) and productivity (2.1 ± 0.3 mg/l) values, poor abundance of phytoplankton (153 ± 35 units/l), zooplankton (69 ± 8 units/l) and benthos (19 ± 4 no./kg), and poor number of species of phytoplankton (21 ± 6 no./l), zooplankton (16 ± 3 no./l) and benthos (14 ± 5 no./kg) were recorded in the effluent contaminated areas of the Sundarbans (The Pashur river and its connected canals sites). Whereas, the previous recorded data (before rapid industrialization and before 2010) of the same study area and the uncontaminated areas of the Sundarbans (Western part of SRF) indicate that the values of total suspended solids (9.5 ± 1.8 mg/l), chemical oxygen demand (133 ± 28 mg/l), total hardness (952 ± 37 mg/l) and oil content (8.1 ± 0.5 mg/l) were lower than those of contaminated areas of SRF (The Pashur rivers and its connected canals sites). Similarly the values of transparency (25 ± 4 cm) and productivity (7.9 ± 0.7 mg/l), and abundance of phytoplankton (369 ± 58 units/l), zooplankton (92 ± 13 units/l) and benthos (37 ± 6 no./kg), and number of species of phytoplankton (38 ± 5 no./l), zooplankton (25 ± 4 no./l) and benthos (26 ± 4 no./kg) of the uncontaminated areas and before rapid industrialization (before 2010) were much higher than those of the contaminated areas of SRF (the Pashur river and its connected canals). Physico-chemical conditions (Table 2) of soil (2-6 inches surface soil) of intertidal zones of the Pashur river and its connected canals sites (The Sundarbans) are being contaminated day by day due to different types effluents of different industries; this contamination is being increased gradually by these industries related shipping activities. High values of total suspended solids, chemical oxygen demand, total hardness and oil content; poor values of productivity and transparency; poor abundance and species diversity of phytoplankton, zooplankton and benthos of water, physico-chemical conditions of soil and air quality (Table 1, 2 & 3) indicate that the study areas of the Sundarbans reserve forest (The river Pashur and its connected canals sites) ecosystems are being changed by the rapid industrialization on the periphery of the Sundarbans. This finding has been supported by the studies of Chowdhury (2009 and 2011), Hossain and Chowdhury (2008), Rahaman *et al.* (2013) and Rahman *et al.* (2006, 2013 and 2014). They had recorded good transparency (27 ± 5 cm), productivity (17 ± 0.8 mg/l), phytoplankton (407 ± 53 units/l) and zooplankton (59 ± 14 units/l) abundance but low values of total suspended solids (9.2 ± 1.4 mg/l), chemical oxygen demands (63 ± 5 mg/l), total hardness (946 ± 53 mg/l) and oil (7.26 ± 0.4 mg/l in water, 3.0 ± 0.2 mg/kg of 2 inch surface soil) in their studies in the Sundarbans.

Chowdhury and Zaman (2001 and 2002) and Bhuiyan (1983) recorded in their studies that different industrial effluents contamination in the water body were responsible for increasing of total suspended solids, COD and total hardness values of water and for decreasing of transparency, productivity and abundance of phytoplankton and zooplankton of water. The recorded data of the industrial effluents contaminated areas of

the Sundarbans have been supported by the observations of Chowdhury and Zaman (2001 and 2002) and Bhuiyan (1983).

More than 10 mg/l of oil in aquatic habitat can be lethal for the aquatic lives (APHA, 1989). Higher content of oil was observed in the water and soil of intertidal zones of the industrial sites of the Sundarbans (Tables 1 and 2). The recorded SPM, NO_x and SO_x values (Table 3) indicate that due to industrialization these values are being increasing in and around the Sundarbans. Therefore, the air, water and soil of the study areas of the Sundarbans (The Pashur river and its connected canals sites) are being polluted and affected by the industrial wastes.

3.2. Phytoplankton, zooplankton and benthos

Diversity and abundance of phytoplankton, zooplankton and benthos of the industrial contaminated (The Pashur river and its connected canals sites SRF) and uncontaminated areas of the Sundarbans (Western part of the SRF), and previous study (before 2010 data) of the Sundarbans indicate that diversity and abundance of phytoplankton, zooplankton and benthos are being decreased in and around the Sundarbans (Industrial sites). Besides, the presence of *Euglena* sp. and *Phacus* sp. (pollution indicator) in study areas also indicates pollution of the aquatic habitat of Sundarbans by industrial effluents and industry related shipping activities (discharge burn oil, wastes, ballast water, etc.). Islam (1973), Chowdhury (2003), Hossain and Chowdhury (2008) reported 44 phytoplankton species with good abundance in different season from the aquatic ecosystems of the Sundarbans before rapid industrialization (before 2010) beside the Sundarbans. So, it can be concluded that the different types of species and abundance of the phytoplankton (primary producer) are being affected by the industrial effluents in aquatic ecosystems of the study sides of Sundarbans. This result has been supported by the findings of Chowdhury and Zaman (2001) as they observed phytoplankton (primary producer) species diversity and abundance always being decreased by the industrial pollution in the aquatic ecosystems. Presence of Protozoa (Zooplankton-pollution indicator) in study areas of the Sundarbans also indicates the pollution of water (Chowdhury and Zaman, 2002). Islam (1974) and Chowdhury (2003 and 2011) recorded good number of zooplankton species in the aquatic ecosystems of the Sundarbans in different seasons. So, it is clear that the zooplankton (primary consumer of water) diversity and abundance of the Sundarbans are being decreased by the industrial and shipping pollutants. Chowdhury and Zaman (2002) also recorded that most of the zooplankton species couldn't survive in the aquatic ecosystem except protozoa when oil content of water became more than 10 mg/l. Chowdhury (2002 and 2011) recorded 34 benthos species in the Sundarbans during his studies and most of the recorded benthos abundance was in good condition. The recorded benthos status of the present study indicates that benthos population and diversity are being affected by the pollutants in the industrial sites of the Sundarbans. Phytoplankton, zooplankton and benthos abundance of the industrial contaminated areas of the Sundarbans showed statistically significant negative correlation with TSS (> -0.872), COD (> -0.790), total hardness (> -0.822) and oil content (> -0.785) values.

Study Location	SPM (mg/m ³)		NO _x (µg/m ³)		SO _x (µg/m ³)	
	Study Period	Before 2010	Study Period	Before 2010	Study Period	Before 2010
Sundarbans area (Industrial sites)	237- 486	115 - 180	24 – 35	12 - 19	21-38	9 – 14
Mongla area	276 – 515	158 - 259	74 -149	56 - 101	56 – 88	40 - 58
Rampal area	241 – 397	132 - 218	62 – 98	53 - 72	43 -74	34 - 50
Sundarbans area (Unindustrial sites)	84 – 116	79 - 114	11 – 16	10 - 14	8 – 12	7-11
EQS- Bangladesh	400		80		80	

3.3. Flora and fauna

The recorded floral and faunal conditions of the industrial contaminated areas and uncontaminated areas have been presented in Table 4.

During the period of study it was observed that some flora and fauna were affected by industrial pollution in many different ways (Table 4). Some of the seedlings of mangrove plants and 'saline water lily' of the intertidal zones were affected by changed physico-chemical conditions of water and soil and they were being decomposed (Table 4). Pneumatophores and some of the seeds of the Sundri plant were found black coloured; more than 70% embryos of the seeds were decomposed, thus their germination would be prohibited. Whereas, almost 100% embryos of the Sundri seeds were found in good condition in the uncontaminated areas (west SRF- without industry). In the Sundarbans, three species of macro red algae (*Catenella* sp.) which remain attached with plant root and pneumatophores, and two species of a brown macro algae (*Colpomenia* sp.) which grow in small creeks as benthic form (Islam, 1973; and Chowdhury, 2003). But these algal flora were found in poor abundance in the industrial sites of Sundarbans compare to without industrial areas (Table 4).

During study period 14 to 20 species of fishes were recorded in the industrial effluents contaminated areas, but 27 to 33 fish species were recorded in the unpolluted areas (Table 4). During breeding season, only 1700-2400 (units/l) eggs and hatchlings of commercially valuable fishes like Parshe (*Liza* spp.), Khorsula (*Mugil* spp.), Bagda shrimp (*Penaeus monodon*), etc. were found in the industrial areas of the Sundarbans; whereas 6300 to 8700 units/l of eggs and hatchlings of those fishes were recorded in the nonindustrial areas (West SRF). In previous study (before 2010) 6800 to 9600 units/l of eggs and hatchlings of these fishes were recorded

Name of the flora and Fauna	Units	Present Study	Non industrial areas	Previous study Before 2010	Comments
Seedling of Plants on intertidal zones	no./m ²	2-3 Observed poor number of the seedlings	10-14	12-19	
Saline water lily on intertidal zones	no./m ²	3-5 Plant bodies were being decomposed	9-15	14-24	Plant bodies were being decomposed due to change of soil & water quality
Fruits/Seeds of Sundri Plants	no./m ²	6-10 >70% seeds embryos were black	12-19	10-19	Black embryos generally be decomposed as a result seed are not germinated
Pneumatophores (Breathing roots) of plants	no./m ²	>20% Pneumatophores growth are been affected.	>95% Pneumatophores are ok.	All pneumatophores are ok.	Physiological activities of the plants may be affected by the pollution
<i>Catenella</i> sp. (3sps.)- a red algae attached with plant roots	no./m ²	35% lower than nonindustrial site	Present in good conditions	Present in good conditions	Worked as primary producer; Source of food and nutrient of the many aquatic animals
<i>Colpomenia</i> sp. (2sps.)- a brown macro algae grows in small creeks as benthic form	no./m ²	Only 4-9% covered area.	Present in good conditions	Present in good conditions	Worked as primary producer; Source of food and nutrient of the many aquatic animals
Eggs & hatchlings of different fishes i.e. Parshe, Khursula, Bagda, Harina etc.	units/l	1700 to 2400 (During breeding season)	6300 to 8700	6800 to 9600	Source of natural and cultivated fish production in the South-west coastal areas of Bangladesh
Mudskippers – a common intertidal zone fish	no./m ²	0-2	2-4	3-7	Indicator of mangrove ecosystem and used as food by the birds, fishing cat, otter, snake and other animals.
Mud Crabs (Kakra) (4sps.) – a common intertidal zone Crustacea	no./m ²	0-1	2-4	3-6	Indicator of mangrove ecosystem and used as food by the birds, crocodiles and other animals.
Snails (Shamuk) (10 sps.) – a common intertidal zone Mollusk	no./m ²	3-7	9-15	10-16	Indicator of mangrove ecosystem and used as food by the fishes, birds, crocodiles and other animals.

Table 4 (Cont.)					
Name of the flora and Fauna	Units	Present Study	Non industrial areas	Previous study Before 2010	Comments
Fishes –common fishes of the rivers, canals, creeks etc.	No. of species	14-20 species	27-33 species	31 - 43 species	Major aquatic resource of the Sundarbans
Frogs (2 spp.) – intertidal zone of the Pashur river & canals	Study period	Few frogs were observed in the study period	Many Frogs were observed in the intertidal zones	Unlimited Frogs were observed in the study area	Common Amphibian of the Sundarbans
Snakes (7 spp.)	Study period	11-15 snakes of 4 species were observed	23-28 Snakes of 7 species were observed	26-33 Snakes of 7 species were observed	Vey Common Reptile of the Sundarbans
Monitor Lizards (3 spp.) – intertidal zone of the Pashur river & canals	Study period	9 monitor lizards were observed in the study period	23 Monitor Lizards of 3 different species were observed	21- 27 Monitor lizards of 3 different species were observed in the study area	Common reptiles of the Sundarbans
Crocodile – common animal of the Pashur river and connected canals	Per day/ study period	Only 3 crocodiles were observed in the study period	4-5 crocodiles were observed in a day	5-6 crocodiles were observed in a day	Threatened species and Indicator of the mangrove ecosystem
Intertidal Bird (Masked finfoot) - intertidal zone of the Pashur river & canals are habitat	Study period	Only 2 Masked finfoot bird was observed in the study period	Only 5 Masked finfoot was observed	29 Masked finfoot birds were observed in the study area	Worldwide Threatened species and only the mangrove bird
Common Birds (Heron, Kingfisher etc. - common animal of the Pashur river and connected canals	Study period	Only 27 birds of 5 different species were observed in the study period	162 birds of 33 different species were observed	More than 300 birds of 46 different species were observed	Common animals of the mangrove ecosystem
Ban Morog (Birds) - common beside the Pashur river and connected canals	Study period	2 Ban Morog were observed in the study period	16 Ban Morog were observed	Ban Morog was available	Common bird of the mangrove ecosystem
Migratory Birds – intertidal zone of the Pashur river & canals are habitats	Study period	No Migratory bird was observed in the study period	Few migratory birds were observed	Many Migratory birds were observed in the study area	The Sundarbans is the habitat of the Migratory birds
Fishing cat - intertidal zone of the Pashur river & canals are habitats Otter – intertidal zone of the Pashur river & canals are the habitats	Study period	Only 3 foot marks of fishing cats were observed in the study period	19 Foot marks of fishing cats were observed	Many foot marks of fishing cat were observed in the study area	Common animal of the Sundarbans
Dolphins - common animal of the Pashur river and connected canals	Study period	2 foot marks of Otter were observed in the study period	12 Foot/ Pug Marks of Otter were observed	Unlimited Foot Marks of Otter were observed	Threatened animal in the main land but a common animal of the Sundarbans
Deer – beside the Pashur river & connected canals	no./hour	7-9 times movements of dolphin were observed/ hour	15-17 times movements were observed/ hour	19-22 times movements were observed / hour in the study area	Threatened species and indicator of the mangrove ecosystem
Wild Boar – beside the Pashur river & connected canals	Study period	Poor no. of deer was observed	Available deer was observed	Unlimited deer were observed in the study area	Common Animal of the Sundarbans
Tiger – beside the Pashur river & connected canals	Study period	11- 16 no. Wild Boars was observed in the study period	24- 30 no. Wild Boars were observed in the study period	Unlimited Wild Boars were observed	A Common Animal of the Sundarbans
Tiger - beside the Pashur river & connected canals	Study period	3-4 tigers pug marks were observed in the study period	11 - 15 tigers pug marks were observed in the study period	9 - 12 tigers pug marks were observed in the study area	Threatened and indicator species of the Sundarbans

in the Sundarbans (Chowdhury, 2011). Present study indicates that the industrial effluents posed profound threat for the eggs and hatchlings of different fishes. During the period of study it was found that mudskippers, mud crabs, and snails diversity and population are being decreased on the intertidal zones of industrial areas of the Sundarbans compare to nonindustrial areas and previous study data. In this study the diversity and abundance of frogs, snakes, monitor lizards, otter and fishing cat were found very poor in the industrial sites

of the Sundarbans areas, whereas these faunal species were in normal conditions in the nonindustrial areas of the Sundarbans (Table 4) as well in previous study. In the industrial sites of the Sundarbans, birds population and diversity were observed in poor conditions compare to nonindustrial sites of the Sundarbans and previous study data (before 2010). In the period of study poor number of dolphin, crocodile, Masked finfoot (worldwide vulnerable mangrove bird), wild boar and deer were recorded in the industrial sites of the Sundarbans areas (The Pashur river and its connected canals, creeks, etc. and their intertidal zones and *char Islands*). Whereas their number of population were comparatively higher in previous study (before 2010) and in nonindustrial sites of the Sundarbans areas (Table 4). Chowdhury (2003, 2011) and IUCN (2001) recorded dolphins, crocodile, Maskedfinfoot, migratory birds, wild boar, deer, etc. in and around the river Pashur and its connected canals and creeks. Royal Bengal Tiger – a threatened and indicator species of the world largest mangrove forest but during the period of study only 3 tigers pug marks were observed in the industrial sites of the Sundarbans areas (The Pashur river and its connected canals, creeks, etc. and their intertidal zones and *char Islands*). Whereas 12 tigers pug marks were recorded in the same study areas in the study of before 2010 and 15 tigers pugmarks were recorded in the nonindustrial sites of Sundarbans areas (Table 4). Status of the tigers indicates that the study area has been loosed habitat quality of the tigers may be continuous changing of air, water and soil quality by the rapid industrialization as well as increasing of industry related shipping activities in and around the Sundarbans.

3.4. River systems and Erosion

The Passur and all its distributaries are tidal channels and is the main river to control drainage systems of the total study and industrialization area. The average elevation of the sites is about 2 m above the mean sea level. The study area slopes gently towards Southwest. Small tributaries and canals that finally join the river Passur and drain the industrialization area. The river Passur flows in Southern direction. The name of connected rivers or tidal channels of the Passur river are Maidara, Mongla, Chunkuri, Ghasiakhali, Bishna, Kumarkhali, Gona, Dagura and Ichhamati rivers and their connected small creeks/ channels, and Biddarbahon Channel, Burirdanga khal, Chak Gona khal, Daudkhali khal, etc. and their small creeks. These rivers/ channels/ creeks/ khals and their all small creeks are situated as like as net in the study areas (growing industrialization areas). All these channels are acting as creeks through which tidal water enters into the study site during high tide and drains out during the ebb tide. The Passur river is the main navigational channel for transportation of the construction materials, imported raw materials, coal, oil, etc. of the different industries. The width of this river varied from 700 to 850 m at different locations; depth varied 6.5 to 8.00 m; catchment area more than 400 sq. km; minimum discharge (6000 m³/s) month is February and minimum depth in dry season 6 to 6.50 m at Mongla; maximum discharge (22500 m³/s) month is August and maximum depth in wet season 8 m at Mongla. The rainfall of the study areas initially stores in the ditches, agricultural lands, shrimp farms and other low lying areas. Aftermath, multiple creeks in the project area receive the rainfall runoff and finally discharge into the Passur River. Maximum surface runoff from this flat or nearly flat land is found during monsoon. This runoff flows to the nearby connected rivers/ canals/ creeks of the Passur river. The tides of the Passur river are important for navigation as determines the possibility of crossing the shallow outer bar at the entrance. The approximate range of the tide observed at Mongla station is between 1.2 m to 3.5 m and the tidal amplitude is around 3.25m (Observation of Mongla Port Authority). The tide is semi-diurnal in nature.

Two tides (e.g., flood and ebb) are regularly observed in the Passur river, which enters into the study sites through numerous connected creeks. Earlier, maximum study areas were inundated because of tidal flooding. Tidal water intruded into the land during high tide, flooded twice in a day and discharged with the creeks during low tide when the river water is in lower stage. The average height off lood tides rise during spring tide and decline during neap tide. Eventually, those areas have been raised due to regular sedimentation with tidal flooding. Semi-diurnal tide (two flood tides in 24 h) occurs in the Passur River, which enters inland area through numerous connected creeks. Within the study area, lands that are not protected by coastal polders are inundated by tidal floods twice in a day. Tidal water intrudes into these lands during flood tide, and flows back to Passur during ebb tide with the numerous tidal creeks. The study sites were dominated by seasonal shrimp cultivation and agricultural practices. These areas were protected by the earthen made local levees, which is the common practice to

prevent tidal inundation of the study area at present. Most of the lands of the study areas (also growing industrialization areas) are occupied by shrimp farms where river water intrusion through tidal creeks is regulated by indigenous earthen made local levees and wooden water control structures. These fragile wooden structures allow river water to enter during flood tide according to the demand of the shrimp farms.

Now, the name and presence of the connected rivers or tidal channels of the Passur river (Maidara, Mongla, Chunkuri, Ghasiakhali, Bishna, Kumarkhali, Gona, Dagura and Ichhamati rivers and their connected small creeks/ channels, Biddarbahon Channel, Burirdanga khal, Chak Gona khal, Daudkhali khal, etc.) and their small creeks are going to be disappeared due to growing industrialization in the study areas. It has been observed that when an industry buy the land for settling industry, they fill up the entire land space for industrial infrastructures and they also fill up all the small canals and wetlands inside their boundary. It has been also observed that natural tidal flow areas are going to be decreased day by day with the growing industrialization in the study areas. The satellite maps of the 1978 and 1998 indicate the presence of Pashur river connected all channels; but the satellite map of 2017 indicates the declined scenario of the connected rivers or tidal channels of the Passur river and their small creeks in the study areas. As a result siltation rate is increasing gradually (Siltation data) on the beds of Pashur river and its connected rivers and channels due to continuous decreasing of natural tidal flow areas of the Pashur river.

Analysis of time-series hydrographic level surveys of BIWTA shows a gradual decline of navigability especially in the reach of Harbaria to Mongla Port. The siltation data of different locations shows gradually decreasing the depth of the Pashur river (beside the Mongla port) and its all connected channels. According to BIWTA data, the Pashur river water depth is above 9 m at Akram point, 8.1 m at Harbaria canal, 7m at Sagir canal, 5.6 m at Chila bazar, 4 m at Coast guard jetty, 6.1 m Mongla port jetty and 4 m at Mongla port berthing Jetty.

On the other hand, the pressure of tidal flows are increasing on the both sides riverbank of the Pashur due to the decreasing of depth of river and declining the natural tidal flow areas. As a result, riverbank erosion is increasing on the both sides of the Pashur river. During the last five years, from proposed Rampal Coal based power plant site to Koromjol (Western riverbank of the Pashur, 22° 26.318' N & 89° 35.281' E) and Joymonirghol (Eastern riverbank of the Pashur, 22° 21.227' N and 89° 38.163' E) areas 130 to 360 m width riverbank erosion were been happened in different locations. Main Baniashanta bazar, old Koromjol Forest offices, old Baniashanta brothel houses, Baniashanta bazar to Dhangmari forest office connected road, etc. became the part of the Pashur river due to massive erosion. River bank erosion also responsible for the increasing of siltation on the river beds and decreasing the depth of the Pashur river in different locations. The rate of siltation, riverbank erosion and current of tidal flow are statistically significant positive correlation ($r = > 0.851$) with each other. It was recorded that the number and activities (anchoring, landing, staying, movement, etc.) of the cargo vessels are being increased with the growing industrialization for different industrial purposes. "The anchoring and movement of the cargo vessels are also enhancing the riverbank erosions" complained by the people of the Baniashanta and Dhangmari areas.

Navigation facilities is essential for coal transportation (raw material of Rampal Coal Power plant) from Akram point to plant site. Mongla Port Authority provides aids to navigation within its port limit only. Besides, BIWTA provides aids to navigation in inland water transportation routes. The channel from Mongla Port Fairway Buoy (MPFWB) to Mongla Port Jetty is properly marked by necessary aids for day time navigation only. Channel from Port Jetty to project site (power plant) is marked by both day time and night navigational facilities e.g. lightened buoy and beacons by BIWTA. Mongla port is located at 14 km south from the proposed Rampal Power plant site. The plant has been envisaged with the aim of using Mongla Port facilities (not berthing/jetty facilities) for primary fuel-coal transportation from source countries to the project coal terminal with the capacity of handling 6.5 million tons in a year. According to the navigational information of Mongla Port Authority, at present, Mongla Port handles 1.6 million tons of cargo yearly. The average turn around time (in day) for a bulk cargo is 5.5 and 2.5 for a container cargo. They are handling 250 vessels in every years. At present, Mongla port operates five general cargo/container berths, seven river mooring berths, and fourteen anchorage berths. In addition, there are seven specialized private berths.

Location	2013 (cm)	2014 (cm)	2015 (cm)	2016 (cm)	2017 (cm)
Harbaria	7-9	10-15	17-20	19-21	20-22
Koromjol	15-19	18-24	25-30	26-37	30-39
Coast Guard Jetty	4-6	6-7	7-8	7-9	8-10
Mongla Port Jetty	11-15	14-19	19-24	26-29	29-33
Mongla Port Berthing Jetty	13-18	16-22	24-30	25-33	27-36

Latitude	Longitude
22.370561 N	89.632661 E
22°21'227' N	89°38'163' E
22°20'901' N	89°38'188' E
22°26'542' N	89°36'071' E
22°28'135' N	89°35'038' E
22°27'989' N	89°35'042' E
22°27'539' N	89°35'057' E
22°27'530' N	89°35'048' E
22°27'529' N	89°35'046' E
22 °26.235' N	89 °35.495' E
22 °26.285' N	89° 35.309' E
22 °26.318' N	89° 35.281' E
22 °26.235' N	89° 35.495' E
22 °26.232' N	89° 35.495' E
22 °26.233' N	89° 35.418' E
22 °26.233' N	89° 35.498' E
22 °26.838' N	89° 35.065' E
22 °26.980' N	89° 35.053' E
22 °27.069' N	89° 35.037' E

“Maintenance of draught is the main challenge for Mongla port” Authority said. Presently, maximum allowable draught at jetty is 6.5 m. Vessels having 6.0 m to 6.5 m draught can take berth at port jetty. So, regular dredging of the above mentioned Pashur channel is necessary for importing necessary coal for the proposed Rampal power plant. According to the guidelines of the Department of Environment of Bangladesh is indicating that without detailed EIA dredging is not possible as the channel is the habitat of the endangered dolphin and it is situated inside the fragile ecosystem of the Sundarbans. Degradation of the natural environmental conditions due to continuous dredging can't be mitigated in any way. Its impacts would be an irreversible mitigation (IM).

Based on the data of the present investigation and conditions of the study areas like physico-chemical conditions of air, water and soil, floral and faunal status it can be concluded that the intertidal zones and the

Loss of house due to riverbank erosion

Loss of house due to riverbank erosion

**Industrialization beside Baniasanta bazar
(at N 22°28'135" & E 89°35'038")**

Established Silo beside the Sundarbans

Industrialization near Joymonirghol

Shipping activities

Erosion inside the Sundarbans

Deer inside the Sundarbans

forest floor besides the river Pashur and its connected canals, creeks of the Sundarbans are being contaminated by the different type of pollutants of the different industries and industry related shipping activities. According to Islam (1982) and Islam (1997), Karim (1988), Hussain and Acharya (1994), Nazrul-Islam (1995), Jahan *et al.* (2000), IUCN (2001), Chowdhury (2003) and Hossain (2014) this areas were free from different type of pollutions. Floral and faunal status indicate that population and diversity of some primary producers, consumers, aquatic animals and plants, and their habitats have already been affected by the pollutants of rapid industrializations besides the Sundarbans. It is a natural habit of crocodile to prepare their hatchling house besides the rivers, canals and creeks during the month of April-May (IUCN, 2001). But due to pollution of water and soil besides the river, canals and creeks crocodiles may not be able to prepare their hatchling house in these areas to lay and hatch their eggs. As a result, crocodile may migrate from their own habitats and face territory conflict and ultimately crocodile's population would be affected. Similarly due to loss of habitat may tigers migrate from the affected parts of the Sundarbans and face territory conflict and may lose their natural breeding capacity. Ultimately, the population of tiger would be decreased and it may become a critically endangered species.

Regeneration of the Sundri trees; population, habit and habitats of mudskippers, mud crabs, snails, monitor lizards, intertidal zone birds (world endangered bird 'Masked finfoot'), common birds, fishing cat, otter, dolphins, crocodile, deer, wild boar and tigers are being affected due to continuous increasing of industrial pollution.

So industrial pollution is a matter to be concerned and long term monitoring and research are necessary to find out the detail information on the long term impact of industrial pollution and self recovery capacity of ecosystem of the Sundarbans. Similarly the rules and regulations of international conventions like Ramsar, UNESCO Natural Heritage Site, Convention of Biological Diversity (DoE 2010), etc. and guideline of MoEF (2010) must be implemented properly and a national and international commitment is necessary to stop all kinds of activities which may create this type of the problem for the fragile ecosystem of the Sundarbans.

Sattar (2010a) described on the emission level of different toxic gases and heavy metals of coal fired power plant. Human health hazards and possible impact on the Sundarbans due to coal-fired power plant have also been discussed by Sattar (2010b). Chowdhury (2017) mentioned the wind flow is indicating that the total study area, i.e., Rampal, Mongla and the Sundarbans will be affected by the toxic gases and ashes of the coal based power plant in different seasons; especially the Sundarbans will be affected during pick tourism period in the month of December to February. It is a matter to be concerned when the Sundarbans reserve forest is already facing threats from natural calamity, deforestation, rise in salinity and extinction of many species mainly due to human carelessness, ignorance and lack of implementation of laws, poaching and illegal wildlife trade (Mannan 2010; Chowdhury 2011; and Hossain 2014). Study of Chowdhury and Akber (2015) on the impacts of oil spill on the Sundarbans indicates that sink of coal, oil and industrial raw materials loaded ship created some problems for the biodiversity and ecological conditions of the Sundarbans. Kingston (2002) addressed the Long-term environmental impact of oil spills.

Environmental Impact Assessment (EIA) of physical, biological, social and economic environment of the Sundarbans and the surrounding areas indicate that the impacts of industrialization are negative and irreversible (-39) which can't be mitigated in any way. It is indicating that climate, topography, land use

pattern, air and water quality, floral and faunal diversity, aquatic ecosystems and capture fisheries of the Sundarbans and the surrounding areas will be affected permanently due to continuous industrialization on the periphery of the Sundarbans and proposed coal fired power plant. Increasing of river erosion, noise pollution and health hazards, loss of culture fisheries, health hazards, and destruction of agriculture will be happened due to unplanned industrialization. These problems may be reversible after long mitigation process except agriculture. But all reversible mitigations are negative (total no. is -58). Mitigation of agricultural loss will be very difficult and many people will become land less. Urbanization, development of markets/ bazaars, transportation and industrialization will be developed which may be sustainable but mitigation must be ensured. The total no. of sustainable mitigation is only +13 which indicates that the study area (Periphery of the Sundarbans) is not suitable for industrialization and urbanization (Table 7). Only electrification in the rural area and very few job, and localized business facilities will be increased by establishing the industries and coal fired power plant. The benefits/facilities of industrialization on the periphery and proposed coal fired power plant of Rampal is poor (S +24) than that of negative impacts.

So environmentally, physically, socially and economically the periphery areas of the Sundarbans are not suitable to establish different type industries including coal based power plant. On the basis of IECs and EIA, industrialization on the periphery of the Sundarbans will be act as "to add insult to injure" on the Sundarbans areas and its fragile ecosystems, flora and faunal diversity. A long term research and intensive monitoring must be done to find out the detail information on the long term impact of industrialization on the biodiversity

Table 7: Environmental Impact Assessment Matrix for industrialization on the periphery of the Sundarbans				
IECs	Present Amount/Frequency	Industrial Impact	Impact Type	Impact Rating
A. Physical Environment				
Climate:	Mean temperature varies from 28.2 ±1.9°C/ 28.4 ±1.5°C Annual mean 268 mm.	Will be increased.	IR	-3
Temp		May slightly decrease.	IR	-1
Rainfall	Highly disturbed in and around the Sundarbans areas. Agricultural land use dominated with rural set up.	May be highly disturbed in all areas.	IR	-5
Topography Land Use		Changed into industrial and unplanned urban land use.	IR	-5
Flooding/water logging Hazard	Low in some parts of Rampal.	Flood hazard will be increased due to earthen filling for new construction.	RM	-3
River Erosion	Common in the Sundarbans, Mongla and Rampal.	Increase river erosion for movement of raw materials loaded cargoes.	RM	-6
Water Pollution	Low	Will be increased due to discharge of effluents, leaching of coal, oil spills and dumping of waste.	RM	-5
Air Pollution	Very poor	Air pollution will be increased by increasing SPM, oxides, hydrides and nitrides gases of carbon, sulfur and nitrogen.	IR	-2
Noise Pollution	Low	Moderate	RM	-3

Table 7 (Cont.)				
IECs	Present Amount/Frequency	Industrial Impact	Impact Type	Impact Rating
B. Biological Environment				
Habitat	About 80% habitats for flora and fauna in the Sundarbans.	Reduced habitats of flora and fauna.	IR	-5
Flora	Among the existing species some are decreasing due to different hazards.	May endanger and extinct of some natural floral species in the Sundarbans, Mongla and Rampal areas.	IR	-6
Wildlife	56 species (5 endangered) of the project area.	More wildlife will be endangered and extinct in and around the Sundarbans.	IR	-7
	Capture Fisheries Meet the 40-45% of fish demand.	Reduced production for increasing pollution in the rivers of Sundarbans and other natural water bodies.	IR	-5
	Culture Fisheries Meet the 55-60% of fish demand.	Reduced production for loss of eggs and fish fries.	RM	-4
Agriculture	Covered by 60% land area.	Reduced area.	RM	-5
C. Social Environment				
Human Settlement	30-40% area covered by settlement.	Decrease human settlement due to land acquisition.	RM	-4
Population of land less	Poor no.	Population of land less will be increased.	RM	-4
Status of husband less Women	Poor no.	No. of husband less women will be increased.	RM	-3
Electricity Facility	Absent in some villages.	Electricity facility will be available in all villages.	S	+8
Health hazards	Poor in the study areas except salinity.	Health hazards will be increased by increasing air and water pollution.	RM	-4
Human Diseases	Prevalence of diarrhea, skin diseases, worm infection and anemia.	Lung and pharyngeal diseases, air and water borne diseases will be increased.	RM	-3
Parasitic Diseases	Dengue, malaria and other parasitic diseases are uncommon.	May increase the parasitic diseases.	RM	-1
D. Economic Environment				
Urbanization	Rural area.	Semi urbanization will be developed.	SM	+4

Table 7 (Cont.)				
IECs	Present Amount/Frequency	Industrial Impact	Impact Type	Impact Rating
Industrialization	More than 300 industries	Increase industrialization and pollution will be increased.	SM	+4
Employment:	Average 10 %.	May slightly increase.	S	+3
Government sector	Average 10 %.	May moderately increase.	S	+6
Industrial sector Business	Average 50 % people involved in business.	Business opportunity will increase.	S	+7
Market and Bazars	Mainly Rampal Bazar; Mongla Port Market and Foylahat.	Increased numbers of markets/ bazars without sanitation condition.	SM	+5
Tourism	Medium.	Tourism will be decreased inside the Sundarbans due to loss of ecosystem and biodiversity of the Sundarbans.	RM	-4
Shipping	Medium	Will increase	RM	-5
Note: S - Sustainable, SM - Sustainable with Mitigation, RM - Reversible with Mitigation, IR - Irreversible.				

and ecological conditions of the Sundarbans before introducing the new industries and coal based power plant around the Sundarbans. Otherwise the fragile ecosystem of the Sundarbans including its buffer zone would be threatened by the pollutants of the industrialization.

4. Conclusion

- The study concluded that the present condition of Sundarbans and its surrounding area has reflected a sign of threatened environment.
- The Sundarbans is a magnificent and unique ecosystem and largest remaining mangrove forest in the world, which are under threat from development.
- The Sundarbans is the sole protector of cyclone and storms, generator of livelihood for local people, wild attraction for tourist and a source of national economy.
- It has lost both floral and faunal diversity by the years. Tigers are disappeared, fishes lost their habitat, trees are affected with unknown diseases, other faunal diversity are also disappeared, erosion is concentrated along the Pashur River, people are being helpless and migrated their occupation
- Bangladesh is a developing country and it needs energy. Industrial development in this area has made revolutionary changes by increasing country's net production and also creating more job opportunity.
- Local people are being enchanted by the job opportunity offered from industrialization but it is not work well (According to the opinions of the local people). Only a few people are being benefitted by offering a low ranked job from different industries.
- These industries have also brought the curse for natural environment of this area by discharging waste, gases, hot water recklessly into river and surrounding water bodies.
- The existing industries are solely responsible for depletion of fish and other natural resources, increasing sedimentation in river as they continuously discharge the industrial waste, effluent, dry ash, etc. reported by local people.

- The “Silo” is a recent major example of industrial deterioration to environment.
- Moreover, the government is moving ahead with the 1320 MW coal fired power plant at the mouth of the Sundarbans in Rampal of Bagerhat, along the Poshur River.
- If coal based power plant operate, damage to Sundarbans is obvious. People who will work in plant will be at greater health risk, would cause a significant damage to aquatic life in rivers and canals network in the Sundarbans mentioned by the local communities (local govt. representatives, govt. officials, local political leaders, journalists, fisherman, farmers, businessman, foresters, civil societies, journalists, workers of the industries, religious leaders, general people, etc.) .
- The forest may can lose its recognition as world heritage site.
- So morale, ‘development’ and ‘environment’ cannot place side by side, development is needed for any country but not by cost for environment.

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